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Model evaluation platform

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Change Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of changes
v0.1	12.02.25	Matthew Hartley, Teresa Zulueta Coarasa	Initial draft
v1.0	24.02.25	Matthew Hartley, Teresa Zulueta Coarasa	Incorporated reviewer comments, fixed diagrams, updated glossary

Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BIA	BioImage Archive
BMZ	BioImage Model Zoo
D	Deliverable
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IoU	Intersection over Union
JSON	Javascript Serialised Object Notation
MIFA	Metadata, Incentives, Formats, Accessibility
ML	Machine Learning
NRMSE	Normalised Root Mean Square Error
OME	Open Microscopy Environment
PSNR	Peak signal-to-noise ratio
PU	Public
RI	Research Infrastructure

ROI	Region of Interest
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index
v	Version
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

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Executive Summary

The AI4Life Model Evaluation Platform has been developed to support a key challenge in long-term growth and usability: the systematic evaluation and selection of machine learning models from the BiImage Model Zoo (BMZ). While the BMZ provides a valuable repository of AI models for life science applications, identifying optimal models for specific experimental datasets is challenging. This platform implements a comprehensive framework for quantitative model assessment, enabling evidence-based selection of appropriate analytical tools for diverse biological imaging applications. The initial release provides a curated set of models and data, and can easily be expanded through the use of tools developed through the project.

The technical implementation leverages high-performance computing infrastructure to facilitate large-scale model inference and evaluation. The platform's architecture supports the execution of BMZ models on OME-Zarr formatted datasets from the BiImage Archive (BIA), incorporating multiple standard performance metrics, including Precision, Recall, Intersection over Union (IoU), Dice coefficient and others. The underlying computational framework is implemented in Python, providing both command-line and programmatic interfaces, and designed for use on scalable compute clusters.

The platform's web-based interface enables bidirectional exploration of model performance through both model-centric and dataset-centric views. Quantitative performance metrics are complemented by visual assessment capabilities, allowing detailed evaluation of model behaviour across diverse experimental conditions. Our future development roadmap encompasses enhanced automation of model and dataset selection protocols, improved BMZ/BIA integration, API implementation for programmatic access, and the incorporation of vector embeddings for data-driven model recommendations. This infrastructure represents a significant advancement in the systematic evaluation of AI models for biological image analysis.

1. Introduction

The BiImage Model Zoo's collections are a valuable resource for life scientists wishing to analyse their imaging data. However, selecting models is a difficult task for non-expert users, particularly when there are multiple models to choose from or their data does not clearly match the model's input training data. On the other hand, a lack of access to a diverse data cohort can prevent model developers from exploring how well their model performs on different datasets.

The model evaluation platform provides two groups of users with useful information. It shows how a range of different analysis models perform on different types of data, allowing life scientists to select the best type of model for their data. It also allows model developers to understand how generally applicable a model is, and if the model is suitable for transfer learning.

2. Description of work

2.1 Selection and curation of models and data

We select models from the BiImage Model Zoo based on their original use case (e.g. nuclear segmentation in 3D fluorescence microscopy images), and assign these use cases as specific task descriptors (so "3D cell segmentation", or "denoising" would be task descriptors on which models can be compared). Where possible, we attempt to select multiple models for a single task (Figure 1).

We select datasets from the BiImage Archive which either a) have experimental data with ground truth annotations for one or more tasks, or b) provide a range of different organisms, morphologies, capture conditions, or experimental setups in order to test how models will perform on different domains. For each curated dataset, we choose regions of interest (particular time points and subsections of larger images) that will be provided as input to the models.

Figure 1 – Workflow for model and dataset selection

2.2 Tools for large-scale model execution

To support the large-scale model inference required for the model evaluation platform, we developed a suite of code designed to be used on compute clusters. The main purpose is to allow users to run machine learning models from the BMZ on image data stored in the BIA (in OME-Zarr format), and to evaluate the performance of these models against reference annotations. The system supports various operations like cropping images, and selecting specific z-planes, time points, or channels for analysis.

The core functionality is implemented through several Python scripts that handle model inference and benchmarking. When used with reference annotations, the system calculates various performance metrics including Precision, Recall, IoU, Dice score, PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio), NRMSE (Normalized Root Mean Square Error), and SSIM (Structural Similarity Index). The code uses libraries like `bioimageio.core` for model

handling, zarr for image data management, and MONAI for computing the evaluation metrics (Figure 2). Users can run the tools either through command-line interfaces or integrate them into their own Python workflows.

Figure 2 – Architecture for large scale model inference

The code is open source, freely available online at <https://github.com/BiolImage-Archive/bia-bmz-integration> and is provided under the permissive Apache license.

2.3 Data integration into a structured format

To integrate model metadata, image dataset metadata, and model evaluation results, we generate a structured JSON representation of model outputs (Figure 3). These provide a

way to work with these results programmatically, as well as a potential route towards developing APIs to work with this information.

```
{
  "model": "affable-shark",
  "study": "S-BIAD1196",
  "dataset_uuid": "e15c585a-5539-4b0a-9575-244e4cebf2da",
  "annotation_data_set_uuid": null,
  "analysis_parameters": {
    "z_slices_analysed": [
      99,
      100
    ],
    "xy_image_crop_size": [
      192,
      192
    ],
    "input_channel_analysed": null,
    "t_slices_analysed": null,
    "prediction_channel": null
  },
  "example_image": "/bioimage-archive/ai-galleries/example-images/example_image_S-BIAD1196_e15c585a-5539-4b0a-9575-244e4cebf2da.png",
  "example_process_image": "/bioimage-archive/ai-galleries/example-images/prediction_image_S-BIAD1196_e15c585a-5539-4b0a-9575-244e4cebf2da_affable-shark.png",
  "example_ground_truth": null,
  "precision": null,
  "recall": null,
  "IoU": null,
  "dice": null
},
```

Figure 3 – Structuring of model evaluation results

Different evaluation results are integrated into a single structure used to build the evaluation platform website.

2.4 Data presentation and website

To display the model evaluation results, we have implemented a dedicated set of web pages that allow browsing, filtering and close inspection of outputs (Figure 4).

The web pages are available at:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/galleries/ai-galleries/>

Users can choose to view model-centric (for comparing performance on different datasets) or dataset-centric (for comparing performance with different models) views.

The BioImage Archive AI Gallery

Explore AI-ready image data and how AI models perform on different datasets

In this page you can explore AI-related datasets and models. You can browse a selection of AI-ready datasets curated to facilitate model development. You can also explore the outputs of several models from the BioImage Model Zoo on a dataset to get an idea of what is the most suitable model for a specific image. Or you can investigate how a model works on different datasets and see how widely applicable the model is.

AI-ready datasets

A collection of AI-ready annotated datasets

Analysed datasets

A selection of datasets analysed using different models

Model Evaluation Platform

A selection of BioImage Model Zoo models applied to BioImage Archive datasets

Figure 4 – Selection page for AI-ready datasets, datasets to which models have been applied, and models used for evaluation

When users select either “Analysed datasets” or “Model Evaluation Platform”, they see information pages describing high-level information about either the models or datasets provided in that collection. They can then select individual models or dataset views. These provide further summary information and links to relevant resources in the BMZ, as well as further navigation within the page (Figure 5).

ALPHA

Model Evaluation Platform

This is a collection of AI models from the BioImage Model Zoo that have been applied to several datasets from the BIA. Here you can visualise the prediction of the models for different images.

AI4Life

BioImage.IO

Filter models that have benchmarking scores:

loyal-squid →

3D UNet Mouse Embryo Fixed

Task: 3D nucleus segmentation

Tags: 3D, nuclei, mouse embryo, fixed tissue, confocal microscopy, semantic segmentation, torchscript, ilastik, U-Net, plantseg, deepimagej, pytorch

noisy-fish →

3D UNet Arabidopsis Ovules Nuclei

Task: 3D nucleus segmentation

Tags: 3D, nuclei, arabidopsis ovule, confocal microscopy, semantic segmentation, plantseg, U-Net, pytorch

affable-shark →

Nuclei Segmentation Boundary Model

Task: 2D nucleus segmentation

Tags: 2D, nuclei, fluorescence microscopy, instance segmentation, U-Net

emotional-cricket →

UNet3D Arabidopsis Apical Stem Cells

Task: 3D cell segmentation

Tags: 3D, cell membrane, arabidopsis ovule, confocal microscopy, semantic segmentation, plantseg, U-Net, pytorch, plant, ilastik

ALPHA **loyal-squid**
3D UNet Mouse Embryo Fixed

V. Bondarenko, A. Wolny
10.5281/zenodo.6383429/7774505

On this page

[Model Information](#)

[Benchmarking](#)

[Model Predictions](#)

[Link to model](#)

Model Information

Description: A 3D U-Net trained to predict the nuclei and their boundaries in fixed confocal images of developing mouse embryo. Voxel size: (0.2×0.2×1 μm³) (XYZ).

Task: 3D nucleus segmentation

Licence: MIT

Tags: 3D, nuclei, mouse embryo, fixed tissue, confocal microscopy, semantic segmentation, torchscript, ilastik, U-Net, plantseg, deepimagej, pytorch

Figure 5 – Example overview of models, and specific model view, with links to BMZ from which descriptions are drawn

Each page then provides tabulated information on performance metrics for the application of that model to different datasets for which ground truth annotations are available, including precision, recall, IoU and Dice scores, as well as ROI information to explain exactly which parts of the image were selected for analysis.

The pages also include graphical representations of model inputs, outputs and ground truth references (from which numerical metrics are calculated). These can be downloaded for further analysis as needed (Figure 6 and 7).

Study	Dataset	Precision	Recall	IoU	Dice	Analysis parameters
S-BIAD1026	Go-Nuclear image dataset	0.999	0.33	0.329	0.496	z_slices_analysed: 126,136
S-BIAD1196	brain cell nucleus patches	0.32	0.155	0.117	0.209	z_slices_analysed: 94,104
S-BIAD1492	Simulated fluorescence images	1	0.376	0.376	0.546	z_slices_analysed: 58,68
S-BIAD1518	Human kidney cortex	0.778	0.171	0.163	0.281	z_slices_analysed: 3,13
S-BIAD1518	Biopsy of diabetic human kidney	0.927	0.177	0.175	0.298	z_slices_analysed: 11,21
S-BIAD1518	Scale-cleared rat kidney	0.751	0.024	0.023	0.046	z_slices_analysed: 1,11
S-BIAD1518	Synthetic cell nuclei	0.973	0.151	0.15	0.261	z_slices_analysed: 58,68
S-BIAD1518	Cleared mouse intestine	0.775	0.256	0.239	0.385	z_slices_analysed: 14,24
S-BIAD1518	BABB-cleared kidney	1	0.139	0.139	0.244	z_slices_analysed: 58,68
S-BIAD1518	Human kidney nephrectomy	0.743	0.001	0.001	0.001	z_slices_analysed: 11,21

Showing 1 to 10 of 10 entries

« ‹ 1 › »

Figure 6 – Table showing model performance on different datasets, with numerical output metrics which can be used for sorting and comparison

Study	Dataset	Original image	Reference annotation	Prediction	Analysis parameters
S-BIAD1026	Go-Nuclear image dataset	 Download	z_slices_analysed: 126,136		
S-BIAD1196	brain cell nucleus patches	 Download	z_slices_analysed: 94,104		
S-BIAD1492	Simulated fluorescence images	 Download	z_slices_analysed: 58,68		
S-BIAD1518	Human kidney cortex	 Download	z_slices_analysed: 3,13		
S-BIAD1518	Biopsy of diabetic human kidney	 Download	z_slices_analysed: 11,21		

Figure 7 – Easy visual comparison of model predictions with ground truth annotations

3. Future expansion

We plan to expand with:

- More automation in model and dataset selection, as well as choosing regions of interest.
- Linking better across BMZ / BIA.

- Adding API access to results.
- Using vector embeddings to recommend models that perform well on data similar to the user's data.

4. Conclusion

One of the key ways in which AI4Life provides value to those developing or working with AI models for biological imaging is through the provision of a central platform (the Biolmage Model Zoo) that hosts many pre-trained AI models. This is a valuable resource for life scientists, but the problem of selecting across multiple models and determining whether a model is likely to perform well on data close to that of the end user is difficult.

The Model Evaluation Platform provides a first step to solving this problem – it provides a user-friendly interface for exploring the ways in which different models apply to different datasets. Where ground truth annotations exist, these can be used for direct numerical metric comparison across models, and where they do not, visual outputs are provided.

Further work will focus on close integration with the Biolmage Model Zoo website, better automation of model and data selection and providing evaluation results via an API. Our longer-term goal is to continually enhance the value of the Biolmage Model Zoo's collections by supporting end-user model selection, and allowing developers to easily compare their models to the state of the art.